

Acid-catalysed rearrangements of allyl 4-hydroxybenzoate and 3-methylbut-2-enyl-4-hydroxybenzoate

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Abstract : On treatment with 75% polyphosphoric acid or TFA-H₂SO₄ (50%) allyl 4-hydroxybenzoate and 3-methylbut-2-enyl-4-hydroxybenzoate afforded 4-hydroxy-3-(2'-hydroxypropyl)benzoic acid and 4-hydroxy-3-(3'-hydroxy-3'-methylbutyl)benzoic acid, respectively. Mechanisms of these reactions are discussed.

Keywords : Polyphosphoric acid, trifluoroacetic acid, acid-catalysed rearrangement, Reimer-Tiemann reaction.

Introduction

Synthesis of organic compounds using mild conditions, experimentally simple methodology and easy separation techniques are still interesting in organic synthesis. Aromatic aldehydes are important building block in synthetic organic chemistry. The phenolic compounds having formyl group at suitable position could be used for controlling/synthesizing various types of organic compounds with fascinating structural moiety. A number of publications and reviews have advocated the use of formylation techniques in synthesizing lot of phenolic aldehydes. The formylation of phenols having electron deficient substituents/groups is, in general, difficult. It has been reported that phenols with carboxyl¹, carbamoyl², alkoxycarbonyl³, bromo⁴ or chloro⁴ groups react with hexamethylenetetramine (HMT) in acidic medium to yield corresponding salicylaldehydes. In connection with our recent research we wanted to synthesize 5-carboxylsalicylaldehyde from 4-hydroxy benzoic acid using Reimer-Tiemann⁵ reaction condition. Very poor yield, recovery of maximum unreacted starting material and formation of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde in Reimer-Tiemann reaction condition encouraged the authors to carry out the said reaction with allyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (1a). However, the reaction did not meet the success. Thus, authors tried to

modify the reaction condition to achieve the target compound.

In this endeavour, authors have chosen allyl 4-hydroxybenzoate (1a) as starting material and subjected under almost similar reaction condition of Suzuki *et al.*⁶. The reaction was carried out in 75% PPA with HMT. The extraction of reaction mixture and column chromatography over silica gel afforded an interesting rearranged product (2a) (yield 60%) instead of target compound along with 4-hydroxybenzoic acid. Formation of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid as side product during the course of reaction is an important evidence in favour of intermolecular mechanistic pathway of the said reaction.

Considering that the product 2a was formed by acid-catalysed rearrangement, these authors decided to study this reaction excluding HMT, as it had no involvement during the course of the reaction. Same product was obtained in good yield in absence of HMT. Similar products were also obtained when the reaction was performed in TFA-H₂SO₄ (50%). However, the reaction with only 50% H₂SO₄ did not give encouraging result. 3-Methylbut-2-enyl-4-hydroxybenzoate (1b) also gave similar products both in PPA or TFA-H₂SO₄ (50%) following the path of Markovnikov's addition.

Probable mechanism for the formation of 2a :

matography over silica gel where pure product was ob-

Scheme 1

Compound 2b was also formed from 1b by similar Markovnikov's type of addition with nucleophilic attack of H₂O at C-3' of the stable carbonium ion possibly through the rout as delineated in Scheme 2.

Probable mechanism for the formation of 2b :

tained (yield 60%) in addition to 4-hydroxybenzoic acid as a side product.

Method-II (Trifluoroacetic acid method) : The mixture of starting material (10 mmol) and TFA (8 ml) was stirred at 100 °C for about 2 h on an oil bath. The reac-

Scheme 2

The structures of the products were characterized by analytical and spectral studies as given below.

In conclusion, a simple reaction technique has been developed for easy rearrangement of allyl 4-hydroxybenzoate and 3-methylbut-2-enyl-4-hydroxybenzoate to 4-hydroxy-3-(2'-hydroxypropyl)benzoic acid and 4-hydroxy-3-(3'-hydroxy-3'-methylbutyl)benzoic acid, respectively.

Experimental

Method-I (Polyphosphoric acid method) : The mixture of starting materials (10 mmol) and 75% PPA (8 ml) was stirred at 100 °C for about 1 h on an oil bath. After the completion of reaction cold water (50 ml) was added, and the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature while being stirred. The reaction mixture was diluted and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The residue obtained after removal of CH₂Cl₂ was subjected to column chro-

matography over silica gel where pure product was obtained (yield 60%) in addition to 4-hydroxybenzoic acid as a side product.

2a : m.p. 128 °C (Found : C, 60.87; H, 6.61. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₂O₄ : C, 60.92; H, 6.57%); ¹H NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.38 (3H, dd, CH₃), 2.08 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, OH-2'), 2.70 (1H, doublet of quartet, H-1'), 2.73 (1H, doublet of quartet, H-1'), 3.76 (1H, m, H-2'), 5.42 (1H, exchangeable with D₂O, Ar-OH), 6.82 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-5), 7.85 (1H, br.d, J 8.5 Hz, H-6), 7.88 (1H, br.s, H-2); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 36.5 (C-1'), 23.9 (CH₃), 69.1 (C-2'), 116.9 (C-5), 123.4 (C-1), 125.8 (C-3), 129.7 (C-6), 129.9 (C-2), 160.2 (C-4), 170.8 (COOH).

2b : m.p. 114 °C (Found : C, 64.01; H, 7.23. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₆O₄ : C, 64.25; H, 7.19%); ¹H NMR (250 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.36 (6H, s, 2-CH₃), 1.83 (2H, t, H₂-2'), 2.05 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, OH-3'), 2.82 (2H, t, H₂-1'), 5.40 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, Ar-OH), 6.80 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-5), 7.83 (1H, br.d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-6), 7.86 (1H, br.s, H-2); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 18.5 (C-1'), 27.2 (2-CH₃), 44.1 (C-2'), 69.5 (C-3'), 119.0 (C-5), 122.8 (C-1), 125.7 (C-3), 129.6 (C-6), 129.8 (C-2), 160.2 (C-4), 170.6 (COOH).

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